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STUDENTS TAKE ON REPEALING K TO 12 PROGRAM

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Former President Benigno Aquino III signed the K to 12 Bill into law in 2013. The program provides a 12-year basic education from Kindergarten to Grade 12. Prior to its implementation, the Philippines had only 10 years of basic education, which did not include Senior High School. The K to 12 Program aims to strengthen students' competitiveness, not only in academics, but also in other tracks such as arts, sports, and technical vocational livelihood. Given that, students will have a clear idea of the path they will take in college. Furthermore, by improving their skills, they will be ready and qualified to work on the job they have mastered.

Since the announcement of the implementation of the K to 12 program in 2012, there have been numerous comments from the general public. Some students and parents are opposed to expanding the curriculum by two years because it will take students much longer to graduate. There were also petitions from concerned citizens and organizations saying that the program is not the solution to unemployment and low-quality education in the Philippines. Former President Benigno Aquino III answered all the concerns in a speech and pledged that *"no one will be left behind on the straight and righteous path."*

At this time, Vice President Sara Duterte also stands as the Secretary of Education. The Education Secretary has been vocal about her plans for education to the public. However, numerous false reports have surfaced on social media claiming that the Vice President will abolish the K-12 program in order to implement the Reserve Officers' Training Corps (ROTC). During the campaign, she stated that if elected, she would push for mandatory military service for Filipinos over the age of 18. According to a survey done by Pulse Asia in June 2022, 69% of Filipinos agreed to the proposed implementation of ROTC in Senior High Schools. However, in September 2022, Duterte proposed that mandatory ROTC should be implemented instead of in college. Several student organizations, including The College Editors Guild of the Philippines (CEGP), immediately condemned the initiative.

Many believe that there are many problems in education that the Department of Education should keep an eye on instead of ROTC. The K to 12 Program is a great initiative to meet students' needs both in education and as competent citizens. They stated that four years in high school is not enough preparation for the task awaiting in college. Students in high school are not expected to be knowledgeable when conducting research, doing speeches, experiments, and many more. Senior High School

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is an excellent opportunity to teach them how to do this so that they do not get overwhelmed in college. The two years that students spend in Senior High School should not go to waste, and they must ensure that students have attained the knowledge, skills, and competencies required to have a promising future ahead of them.

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